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[A New Image Mining Approach for Detecting Micro-Calcification in Digital Mammograms](#)

ABSTRACT: Although mammography is typically the best method to detect breast cancer, it does not recognize 3–20% of the cancer cases. Mammography has established itself as the most efficient technique for detecting tiny cancerous tumor and micro-calcifications are the most difficult to detect since they are very small (0.1–1.0 mm) and they are almost contrasted against the images background. The main purpose of this paper is to provide a new method for the automatic diagnosis of micro-calcification in digital mammograms. It is based on image mining, and the results show 97.35% accuracy, which is improved than the previous works. Tests are based on the standard images data corpus, MIAS. The practical result of this research is registered as an invention in the Patents and Industrial Property Registration Organization numbered as 83119.

Keywords: Algorithm, Computational Geometry, Robotics, Motion Planning, Data Science, Artificial Intelligence, Graph, Data Mining, Clustering, Trajectory.

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